

In addition to the outcomes presented above, two key impacts were found: *fostering meaningful behaviour* and *cultivating positive views toward science*. The figures below summarise the subcategories, or specific impacts, for students from citizen science participation. For example, teachers believe that citizen science can help promote custodianship which refers to looking after their lands and the environment.

Evaluating citizen science in schools

Teachers have also shared their views on how to evaluate citizen science in schools and stated that evaluation should include both project evaluation and learning assessments. One of the key findings showed there is a need to assess the suitability of citizen science projects for schools before implementing them in schools. Such an evaluation should consider the following:

- **Aims/goals of citizen science projects** – what does the citizen science project hope to achieve (e.g., understand how temperature and rainfall changes impact plants and animals in Australia).
- **Project resourcefulness** – what resources are provided to enable participation and how useful these resources are in helping teachers engage their students with citizen science.
- **Level of student engagement** – looking at how engaged the students are when they participate in citizen science once the projects have been implemented in schools.

Next steps

This research will be used to identify citizen science projects which would be suitable for schools and student engagement and support our research assessing the outcomes stated by teachers. We are planning to pilot citizen science workshops in schools in collaboration with citizen science project leaders and teachers to engage students with suitable projects identified. LBD has compiled a list of projects that align with the curriculum by [mapping citizen science](#) projects to Stage 4 of the NSW Syllabus.

For more information on our research projects see: <https://lbdscience.com/learning-by-doing-research>

We would like to thank all the teachers who participated in this research for sharing their experiences and ideas on perceived outcomes and impacts for students and ways to assess and evaluate citizen science in schools.

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